

Theological and Sociopolitical Perspectives on the Doctrine of Martyrdom in Islam

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Abstract

This study seeks to examine the theological underpinnings the doctrine of martyrdom in Islamic context, with references to Islamic principles found in the Qur'an, specifically the notion of testing believers through loss and hardship. The article also reflects on the socio-political implications of martyrdom and sacrifice within modern Islamic movements, as well as the consequences of radical resistance in the context of conflicts such as that between Hamas and Israel. Despite the fact that the conflicts in the middle east are multifaceted and complex religious, social and historical challenges, the ongoing brutality in Gaza which has so far killed tens of thousands of innocent civilians including more than 70% women and children raises concern about the interpretations and hermeneutics of the Martyrdom and civil and criminal liabilities arising from such interpretations.

Keywords: Martyrdom, Gaza, Palestine, Middle East, Jihad

Introduction

In a recent interview, Professor Sadegh Zibakalam, a prominent legal scholar in University of Tehran-Iran, commented that in the event of a Western attack on Iran, "not even a single lamppost would remain intact."¹ Professor Zibakalam's assertion may appear extreme, but after assassination of Ismael Haniye in Tehran-Iran² taps into a deeper Islamic and cultural worldview wherein struggles and tests of faith and revenge is closer than anytime in the contemporary history of Iran and the reference to the Islamic values are clear and are interpreted as religious duties (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a) which is seen as divinely ordained trials. The notion that God engages His believers in forms of divine trials is rooted in various Islamic narratives, including the story of Ibrahim (Abraham) and the sacrifice of his son, and the trials mentioned in the Qur'an:

Surah As-Saffat (37:102):

"And when he [his son] was old enough to walk with him, he [Ibrahim] said, 'O my son, indeed I have seen in a dream that I [must] sacrifice you, so see what you think.' He said, 'O my father, do as you are commanded. You will find me, if Allah wills, of the steadfast.'"

Surah As-Saffat (37:103-107):

"And when they had both submitted and he put him down upon his forehead, We called to him, 'O Abraham, you have fulfilled the vision.' Indeed, We thus reward the doers of good. Indeed, this was the clear trial. And We ransomed him with a great sacrifice."

¹ Ensaf News, retrieved from : <https://ensafnews.com/343273/%D8%A7%DA%AF%D8%B1-%D9%85%D8%B0%D8%A7%DA%A9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%B4%DA%A9%D8%B3%D8%AA-%D8%A8%D8%AE%D9%88%D8%B1%D8%AF-%DA%86%D9%87-%D9%85%DB%8C%E2%80%8C%D8%B4%D9%88%D8%AF%D8%9F-%D9%BE%D8%A7%D8%B3/> [In Persian]

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https://fa.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D8%AA%D8%B1%D9%88%D8%B1_%D8%A7%D8%B3%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%B9%D8%8C%D9%84_%D9%87%D9%86%DB%8C%D9%87

Such tests are considered mechanisms by which a believer's faith, courage, and righteousness are evaluated.

This article examines this concept through the lens of both religious doctrine and political realities, particularly in the context of contemporary conflicts. The article ultimately seeks to explore the dangers that arise when governments gamble with the lives and well-being of their people in pursuit of divine or ideological goals. Additionally, it is necessary to mention that any interpretations from and Within Quran, are particularly very sensitive and can be misunderstanding (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b)

Theological Insights: Tests and Trials in the Qur'an

The concept of testing believers is deeply rooted in Islamic theology, as evident from several verses in the Qur'an. In Surah Al-Baqarah, for instance, God says:

“And We will surely test you with something of fear and hunger and a loss of wealth and lives and fruits, but give good tidings to the patient” (Qur'an, 2:155).

Here, the Qur'an speaks of trials that believers must endure, with the ultimate promise of reward for those who show patience and perseverance. This notion of divine tests resonates strongly with the story of Ibrahim (Abraham), who was commanded by God to sacrifice his son—a test of his faith that has since become a cornerstone of Islamic tradition. The willingness of Ibrahim to comply with God's command can be interpreted as a form of divine gamble, where the stakes are faith, life, and the future of his lineage.

This divine testing, however, is not arbitrary but is framed within the larger context of cultivating moral and spiritual strength. The trials mentioned are often viewed as ways to reinforce a believer's commitment to God and the ethical values He endorses.

Theological Underpinnings of the Doctrine of Martyrdom in the Islamic Context

The concept of martyrdom, or *shahada*, holds a highly revered place within Islamic theology, embodying the ultimate act of devotion and sacrifice in the path of Allah. Derived from the Arabic root word *sh-h-d*, meaning "to witness," martyrdom in Islam is understood as bearing witness to the truth of God's sovereignty through the

willingness to sacrifice one's life for the sake of preserving faith, justice, and righteousness. This doctrine is rooted in both the Qur'an and Hadith, and it reflects a complex interplay between spiritual transcendence, communal identity, and the defense of Islamic values.

In the Qur'an, the martyrs (*shuhada*) are exalted as those who are granted an elevated status in the afterlife. The verse, "*And do not say of those who are killed in the way of Allah, 'They are dead.' Rather, they are alive, but you perceive it not*" (Qur'an, 2:154), reflects the belief that those who die in the cause of Allah are granted eternal life. Martyrdom is thus not seen as the end of existence, but rather as a transition to a higher state of spiritual reward and proximity to God. The reward for such sacrifice is described in several verses as immediate entrance into paradise, where the martyr is absolved of sins and honored. Martyrdom is mentioned in several verses in Quran including:

- **Surah Al-Baqarah (2:154)**
"And do not say of those who are killed in the way of Allah, 'They are dead.' Rather, they are alive, but you perceive it not."
- **Surah Al-Baqarah (2:207)**
"And of the people is he who sells himself, seeking means to the approval of Allah. And Allah is kind to [His] servants." (This verse is interpreted as referring to those who sacrifice themselves for the cause of Allah.)
- **Surah Aal-E-Imran (3:169-170)**
"And never think of those who have been killed in the cause of Allah as dead. Rather, they are alive with their Lord, receiving provision, rejoicing in what Allah has bestowed upon them of His bounty..."
- **Surah At-Tawbah (9:111)**
"Indeed, Allah has purchased from the believers their lives and their properties [in exchange] for that they will have Paradise. They fight in the cause of Allah, so they kill and are killed..."
- **Surah An-Nisa (4:74)**
"So let those fight in the cause of Allah who sell the life of this world for the Hereafter. And he who fights in the cause

of Allah and is killed or achieves victory – We will bestow upon him a great reward."

- **Surah An-Nisa (4:95)**

"Not equal are those believers remaining [at home] – other than the disabled – and the mujahideen, [who strive and fight] in the cause of Allah with their wealth and their lives. Allah has preferred the mujahideen through their wealth and their lives over those who remain [behind], by degrees."

- **Surah Al-Hajj (22:58-59)**

"And those who emigrated for the cause of Allah and then were killed or died – Allah will surely provide for them a good provision. And indeed, it is Allah who is the best of providers."

The Hadith literature further emphasizes the spiritual merits of martyrdom. The Prophet Muhammad is reported to have said, *"No soul that has a good standing with Allah and enters Paradise would wish to return to this world, even if it were given everything in it, except for the martyr who, on seeing the virtue of martyrdom, would wish to return to this world and be killed again"* (Sahih Muslim 1877). This underscores the valorization of martyrdom as not only an act of self-sacrifice but as a spiritual aspiration with profound rewards.

However, martyrdom in Islamic thought is not simply an individual pursuit of spiritual rewards; it is also closely tied to the defense of the Muslim community and the upholding of justice. The Qur'an repeatedly calls upon believers to engage in *jihad* (struggle) in defense of their faith and to resist oppression and injustice. This broader understanding of *jihad* includes both the internal struggle for moral purity and the external struggle against forces that threaten the Islamic community. Martyrdom, in this context, is seen as the ultimate expression of one's commitment to protecting the community and ensuring the survival of Islam.

Nonetheless, Islamic jurisprudence places clear boundaries on the pursuit of martyrdom. While the Qur'an sanctions defensive warfare, it also emphasizes justice, restraint, and the protection of non-combatants. The verse, *"Fight in the way of Allah those who*

fight you but do not transgress. Indeed, Allah does not like transgressors” (Qur'an, 2:190), cautions against excesses in conflict, highlighting that martyrdom must align with ethical conduct and justice.

This balance between the glorification of martyrdom and the emphasis on ethical warfare is central to the theological underpinnings of the doctrine. Martyrdom is celebrated within Islam not as a reckless pursuit of death, but as a sacred act undertaken in the service of God and the defense of core Islamic principles. It is this commitment to both spiritual and communal integrity that defines the Islamic understanding of martyrdom, making it a profound yet highly regulated aspect of the faith.

Modern Political Ramifications: Martyrdom and Conflict

The application of these religious concepts to modern political contexts, however, can be problematic. Groups such as Hamas often draw upon the notion of martyrdom and divine trials to justify their actions in the conflict with Israel. Acts of resistance and sacrifice, while seen as noble in some religious perspectives, often result in widespread suffering and destruction. The ongoing conflict between Israel and Hamas is a testament to this—while there is admiration for the courage of the fighters, the material and human costs are immense and enduring.

Martyrdom, in its original sense, is an individual act of sacrifice for a higher cause. However, when this concept is extended to the societal level, as is often done by political or militant groups, it can lead to the deterioration of social order and infrastructure. Zibakalam's remark regarding the destruction of infrastructure in the event of an attack on Iran could be interpreted as a warning against the state's potential over-reliance on martyrdom as a defense strategy. While groups like Hamas may engage in asymmetrical warfare with limited material consequences for the broader society, a nation-state like Iran cannot afford to gamble with the same level of impunity.

The Dangers of Political "Gambling" with National Interests

The danger of governments engaging in such "gambles" with their people's lives and societal progress is evident when examining the recent history of the Middle East. The Iran-Iraq war, which lasted eight years, claimed hundreds of thousands of lives and severely hindered Iran's development. Although framed as a defense of the Islamic Revolution, the human and economic toll was immense, leading to a generation of war-torn communities and halted progress.

Theologically, the Qur'an emphasizes justice and the preservation of human dignity. Any form of governance that risks these principles in pursuit of ideological or divine goals can be seen as deviating from core Islamic tenets. Engaging in high-stakes political or military gambles with adversaries such as the United States or Israel, as some elements within the Iranian government have considered, could have devastating consequences for the nation's stability and future prosperity.

The Qur'an warns against transgressing the bounds of justice in warfare:

"And fight in the way of Allah those who fight you but do not transgress. Indeed, Allah does not like transgressors" (Qur'an, 2:190).

This command to avoid transgression suggests that while defense is justified, reckless or disproportionate actions that lead to widespread destruction are not.

Conclusion

Professor Zibakalam's remarks, though initially framed within the context of Iran's national defense, raise broader questions about the ethical and theological limits of sacrifice and struggle. The Qur'anic verses on testing believers emphasize patience and resilience, but they also underscore the importance of justice and the preservation of life. When such tests are extended to the realm of governance,

leaders must be cautious not to interperert recklessly with their people's future under the guise of divine trial or martyrdom.

A government, unlike a militant group or faction, has civil liabilities and responsibility to protect and nurture the society it governs. While individual acts of martyrdom may be glorified within certain narratives, expanding this ideology to the state level can lead to irreversible damage to the fabric of society. Therefore, as Zibakalam suggests, the Iranian state must carefully weigh the costs of engaging in conflicts that could jeopardize the very survival of its national infrastructure and the well-being of its people.

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